

FINAL REPORT – INEST Project – Call for Young Researchers – Spoke n.1

Progetto Ecosistema dell'innovazione
"Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation
Ecosystem (iNEST)"
Missione 4
Componente 2
Investimento 1.5
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MAIN RESPONSIBLE	Salvatore Raniolo
POSITION	Assegnista di ricerca
PROJECT TITLE	iMAP – integrated Monitoring of Alpine Pastures
REFERENCE PERIOD	30/04/2024-30/03/2025
SPOKE	1
RESEARCH TOPIC (WP/RT)	RT2
WORKPLACE	Dipartimento DAFNAE

Project Principal Investigator (PI)

REPORT STRUCTURE

1. Summary report of activities carried out

The iMAP project, developed within the iNEST innovation ecosystem, aimed to apply innovative technologies for monitoring silvo-pastoral systems, with the goal of identifying management strategies to enhance the ecosystem services linked to mountain grasslands. In particular, the results may be used to formulate guidelines for the zootechnical management of alpine pastures, aimed at enhancing their multifunctionality.

1.1 Objectives

The main objectives of the project were:

- Identification of the main factors determining movement and grazing use by sheep and cattle, outlining potential impacts on productivity, animal welfare, biodiversity and its functions;
- Identification of molecular indicators of taxonomic and functional soil biodiversity and verification of possible simplified approaches for measuring interactions with greenhouse gas fluxes;
- Evaluation of the use of remote sensing indices to estimate vegetation characteristics and grazing intensity;
- Proposal of animal-vegetation-soil relational models, qualitatively integrating the components and relationships to establish an operational framework that can be quantitatively implemented both within the project and in future investigations;
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of prevention practices to reduce conflicts with wildlife.

1.2 Methodology

The project involved two alpine pastures as study areas (Fig. 1):

- Pasture on Monte Coppolo (Lamon – Belluno) between 1,800 and 1,900 m above sea level. The pasture had been abandoned for several years and only since 2023 has it been used again by sheep of the local Lamon breed;
- Pasture at Passo Rolle (Tonadico – Trentino) between 1,800 and 1,900 m above sea level, which has been grazed by dairy cows of various breeds for over a century.

Fig. 1 Study areas used during the iMAP project located in North-East Italy: Malga Juribello pasture (red diamond) and Monte Coppolo pasture (yellow diamond)

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The methodological approach was based on the integration of multiple methods (Fig. 2):

- Illumina sequencing for the characterization of the taxonomic composition at ASV level of soil bacterial and fungal communities, following DNA extraction and purification with standardized kits;
- Inference of functional profiles based on taxonomic composition using FAPROTAX (Louca et al. 2016) and FUNGuild (Nguyen et al. 2016) for bacteria and fungi respectively;
- qPCR for the quantification of gene copies of target genes for specific processes of Nitrogen and Carbon cycles from DNA extracted and purified from soil using standardized kits (Raniolo et al. 2023);
- GPS tracking of sheep and cattle through collars equipped with GPS sensors (2-minute fix schedule) and tri-axial actinometers with a 5-minute fix schedule (Raniolo et al. 2022; Raniolo et al. 2023);
- Vegetation sampling throughout the entire summer season for assessment of floristic composition (Pornaro et al., 2013);
- Remote sensing monitoring based on the Sentinel-2 system (ESA) of the study areas, with focus on spectral indices related to vegetation (NDVI and derivatives – Myneni et al. 1995; Shariatnajafabadi et al. 2014);
- Monitoring of methane and nitrous oxide soil emissions through the use of GASMET T5000 (Hiss et al. 2024);
- Monitoring of the sheep flock on Monte Coppolo through a camera trap system to evaluate the effectiveness of prevention practices for reducing conflicts with wildlife.

Fig. 2 Integrated approach used in the iMAP project with focus on molecular methods applied to soil investigation

1.3 Project Phases

The project followed a structured path divided into three phases to monitor the pastures on Monte Coppolo (Lamon – Belluno) and at Passo Rolle (Tonadico – Trento).

The first phase involved the online acquisition of data for the study areas (DTM, river routes, land use) and their preparation in GIS cartographic databases. During this phase, consumable materials and sensors (camera traps) were purchased, and the experimental designs used in the second phase were prepared.

The second phase involved the collection of pasture samples (soil, vegetation and FTIR spectra of greenhouse gases emitted from soil), the installation of camera trap systems and the application of GPS collars on the animals, the latter at the beginning of the transhumance. Specifically, sample collection covered 3 periods for the Passo Rolle pasture (pre-transhumance, during transhumance and post-transhumance), while for Monte Coppolo only 2 periods were possible (pre and post-transhumance) due to adverse weather conditions. The installation of camera trap systems involved only the Monte Coppolo pasture, with the installation of two fixed and four mobile camera traps, moved together with the electrified nets during the rotation of the fenced sections.

The third phase involved downloading remote sensing spectra for vegetation (NDVI) from the ESA Copernicus portal and processing them into geotiff format maps and geodatabases, subsequently integrated with data obtained from GPS tracking and pasture vegetation compositions. During this phase, laboratory molecular analyses of the collected soil samples were also carried out, along with statistical processing of the data obtained during the project, leading to the development of the integrated operational framework for monitoring silvo-pastoral systems.

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1. Results obtained from the project in relation to the proposed objectives

The analyses of pedological measurements regarding the content of Nitrate (NO_3), Ammonium (NH_4) and organic Carbon (Corg) in relation to the vegetation types found in the Malga Juribello and Monte Coppolo pastures (Poion, Nardion, Deschampsia cespitosa) revealed distinct and significant patterns with respect to the NO_3/NH_4 and Corg/ NO_3 ratios, identified as indicators for the transformation-availability of nitrogen forms and of available substrate for denitrification, respectively. Specifically, the NO_3/NH_4 ratio was significantly higher in areas with high D. cespitosa coverage compared to the others (Fig. 3 – Tab. 1). The Corg/ NO_3 ratio, on the other hand, was significantly higher in Nardion areas and lower in the remaining ones (Fig. 3 – Tab. 1). Both pedological indicators proved stable across the monitored periods.

Fig.3 Weighted means of the NO_3/NH_4 and Corg/ NO_3 ratios in relation to vegetation types (Poion, Nardion, Deschampsia cespitosa) in the Malga Juribello and Monte Coppolo pastures.

Tab.1 Effects and Weighted means of the NO_3/NH_4 and Corg/ NO_3 ratios in relation to vegetation types (Poion, Nardion, Deschampsia cespitosa) in the Malga Juribello and Monte Coppolo pastures.

	NO_3/NH_4			Corg/ NO_3		
	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)
(Intercept)	0.655	1	0.418	6.443	1	0.0111 *

Vegetation	10.366	2	0.00561	**	7.145	2	0.0281	*
Period	1.836	1	0.175		0.045	1	0.832	
Year	0.913	1	0.339		0.1202	1	0.728	
macro_area	3.0324	1	0.0816		1.253	1	0.262	
Vegetation:period	0.8205	2	0.663		0.0202	2	0.989	
R ²			0.254				0.23	
RMSE			1.374				1.258	

	NO ₃ /NH ₄		Corg/NO ₃	
Vegetation	Predicted	95% CI	Predicted	95% CI
<i>Poion</i>	0.33	0.18, 0.62	0.53	0.30, 0.93
<i>Nardion</i>	0.13	0.06, 0.25	1.24	0.66, 2.36
<i>D. cespitosa</i>	1.12	0.37, 3.38	0.16	0.06, 0.44

With respect to the two types of pasture use (Intensive-Int – Extensive-Est) found in the Malga Juribello pasture, the two ratios NO₃/NH₄ and Corg/NO₃ showed significant relationships but with opposite behaviours. Specifically, the NO₃/NH₄ ratio was significantly higher in intensive areas and on average greater than 1 (Fig. 4 – Tab. 2), revealing a greater accumulation of nitrates in the most heavily used areas. Conversely, the Corg/NO₃ ratio was significantly higher in extensively used areas, exceeding the value of 1 in these (Fig. 4 – Tab. 2), revealing a greater availability of Corg, and therefore available energy, for the denitrification ratio. In this context as well, the indicators showed stability across the monitored periods.

Fig.4 Weighted means of the NO₃/NH₄ and Corg/NO₃ ratios in relation to the types of pasture use (Intensive-Int – Extensive-Est) in the Malga Juribello pasture .

Tab.2 Effects and Weighted means of the NO₃/NH₄ and Corg/NO₃ ratios in relation to the types of pasture use (Intensive-Int – Extensive-Est) in the Malga Juribello pasture.

	NO ₃ /NH ₄			Corg/NO ₃			
(Intercept)	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)	
	7.481	1	0.00624	**	0.0064	1	0.936

pasture-use type	7.747	1	0.00538	**	12.0704	1	0.000512	***
period	0.136	2	0.934		0.627	2	0.730	
year	2.0176	1	0.155		0.618	1	0.431	
pasture-use type:period	0.0753	2	0.963		0.412	2	0.813	
R ²			0.316				0.384	
RMSE			1.379				1.23	

Type	NO ₃ /NH ₄		Corg/NO ₃	
	Predicted	95% CI	Predicted	95% CI
int	1.03	0.58, 1.82	0.17	0.10, 0.28
est	0.18	0.10, 0.31	1.03	0.62, 1.72

The analysis of the abundances of individual microbial genes, responsible for the translation of specific enzymes for nitrogen cycle reactions, revealed their tendency to diversify in terms of abundance with respect to vegetation types across the investigated pastures and with respect to use intensity in the Malga Juribello pasture. Specifically, the genes linked to nitrification processes (*amoAa* – *amoAb*) and denitrification (*nirK*, *nirS* and *nosZ*) were found to be more abundant in pasture areas characterized by Poion (Poeto) and *D. cespitosa* (Fig. 5) across all monitored years. Regarding pasture use intensity, the denitrification genes (*nirS*, *nirK*, *nosZ*) and *amoAa* (nitrification) showed a tendency to be more abundant in intensive areas, while *amoAb* (nitrification) and *nifH* (free nitrogen fixation) were more abundant in extensive areas (Fig. 5). Finally, the gene abundance analyses did not reveal significant differences between the monitored periods.

Fig.5 PCA biplot (first two dimensions – PC) of the microbial genes involved in the Nitrogen cycle, analysed and classified in relation to vegetation types (Poion-Poeto, Nardion-Nardeto, Deschampsia) in the Malga Juribello and Monte Coppolo pastures, and to pasture use intensity (Intensive-Int – Extensive-Est) in the Malga Juribello pasture

The microbial communities, considering both bacterial and fungal ones, were analysed separately for the two pastures.

Regarding the Monte Coppolo pasture, the community analysis highlighted a significant tendency to differentiate according to vegetation types (Deschampsia cespitosa, montane Nardeto, subalpine rich Nardeto, Poeto) and period (Pre-grazing – Post-grazing; Tab. 3). Such differences were also found in bacterial functions linked to nitrogen and carbon cycles, with clear distinctions between montane Nardeto and the remaining types, which in turn proved to be distinct from each other (Fig. 6). Despite the distinctions identified, however, the vegetation types showed a reduced number of functions specifically linked to them (Tab. 4).

Tab.3 Results of the PERMANOVA model (Anderson, 2001) for testing the diversity between microbial communities of the Monte Coppolo pasture

	Df	SumOfSqs	R ²	F	Pr(>F)	Dispersion - p
				7.012		
periodo	1	0.147	0.0871	1	0.0358 *	0.441
vegetazione	3	0.138	0.0817	2.193	0.0341 *	0.298
profondità	1	0.0253	0.0149	1.206	0.267	0.647
periodo:vegetazione	3	0.113	0.0666	1.788	0.0712 .	
periodo: profondità	1	0.00673	0.00398	0.320	0.895	
Residual	60	1.261	0.745			
Total	69	1.692	1			

Fig.6 Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) based on Hellinger dissimilarity of nitrogen-carbon (N-C) functions among four vegetation community types of the Monte Coppolo pasture: Deschampsia cespitosa

(light green), montane Nardeto (yellow), subalpine rich Nardeto (blue) and Poeto (red). Small points represent individual sites, while larger central points indicate the centroids of each group.

Tab.4 Microbial functions significantly associated with different vegetation types, period, depth and management practices at the Monte Coppolo pasture. Statistical significances are indicated with asterisks ($p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ **, $p < 0.001$ ***)

Nardion	stat	p.value
cellulolysis	0.467	0.0004 ***
aerobic_chemoheterotrophy	0.452	0.0009 ***
chemoheterotrophy	0.446	0.0011 **
Poion	stat	p.value
hydrocarbon_degradation	0.32	0.0247 *
pre-grazing	stat	p.value
fermentation	0.415	0.005 **
nitrogen_respiration	0.304	0.01 **
nitrate_respiration	0.304	0.01 **
hydrocarbon_degradation	0.23	0.035 *
post-grazing	stat	p.value
cellulolysis	0.389	0.005 **
aerobic_chemoheterotrophy	0.382	0.01 **
chemoheterotrophy	0.358	0.01 **
0-10cm (profondità)	stat	p.value
nitrite_respiration	0.317	0.0075 **
chemoheterotrophy	0.306	0.0077 **
aerobic_chemoheterotrophy	0.295	0.0092 **

Regarding the Malga Juribello pasture, the community analysis highlighted a significant tendency to differentiate according to use intensity (Intensive – Extensive; Tab. 5) and a tendency related to period. Such differences were also found in bacterial functions linked to nitrogen and carbon cycles, with clear distinctions between intensively and extensively used areas (Fig. 7). Despite the distinctions identified, the use types showed a modest number of functions specifically linked to them (Tab. 6). Specifically, extensive areas were found to be more related to methane production and consumption, while intensive areas were more related to the metabolism of aromatic organic compounds and nitrate reduction (an intermediate process of denitrification).

Tab.5 Results of the PERMANOVA model (Anderson, 2001) for testing the diversity between microbial communities of the Malga Juribello pasture

	Df	SumOfSqs	R ²	F	Pr(>F)	Dispersion - p
periodo	2	0.129	0.0747	1.856	0.0789 .	0.430
intensità d'uso	1	0.164	0.0948	4.713	0.0061 **	0.299
profondità	1	0.0536	0.0310	1.541	0.176	0.204

periodo:intensità d'uso	2	0.0445	0.0257	0.639	0.696
intensità d'uso: profondità	1	0.015	0.00867	0.431	0.782
Residual	38	1.323	0.765		
Total	45	1.730	1		

Fig.7 Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) based on Hellinger dissimilarity of nitrogen-carbon (N-C) functions between two types of pasture use at the Malga Juribello pasture: extensive use (light green) and intensive use (red). Small points represent individual sites, while larger central points indicate the centroids of each group.

Tab.6 Microbial functions significantly associated with different use intensities, period, depth and management practices at the Malga Juribello pasture. Statistical significances are indicated with asterisks ($p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ **, $p < 0.001$ *)

Extensive	stat	p.value
methanotrophy	0.388	0.0034 **
methylotrophy	0.387	0.0035 **
aerobic_nitrite_oxidation	0.306	0.0255 *
methanogenesis	0.289	0.0247 *
Intensive	stat	p.value
aromatic_hydrocarbon_degradation	0.366	0.003 **
aliphatic_non_methane_hydrocarbon_degradation	0.366	0.003 **
fermentation	0.322	0.0235 *
nitrate_reduction	0.318	0.0335 *
aromatic_compound_degradation	0.315	0.0205 *
pre-grazing	stat	p.value
nitrite_respiration	0.375	0.025 *

methanol_oxidation	0.302	0.05	*
post-grazing	stat	p.value	
aerobic_nitrite_oxidation	0.342	0.035	*
0-10cm (profondità)	stat	p.value	
aerobic_chemoheterotrophy	0.473	0.0007	***
chemoheterotrophy	0.461	0.0018	**
cellulolysis	0.332	0.0215	*

Regarding the relationships between pedological conditions and soil microbial functions, the analysis highlighted a significant tendency for the correlation between $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NH}_4^+$ and the functional diversity of microbial communities and the abundance of key genes of the nitrogen cycle (Fig. 8). In particular, the $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NH}_4^+$ ratio showed a positive relationship with the functional dissimilarity of microbial communities (Mantel test: $R = 0.36^{***}$; Mantel, 1967), suggesting a potential regulatory role of this pedological condition in structuring N-C functions. These findings were further confirmed by the correlations between pedological conditions and gene abundances, where significant associations were observed between NO_3^- and nitrification genes (*amoAa*) and denitrification genes (*nirK-nirS*, *nosZ*), as well as inverse correlations between $\text{Corg}/\text{NO}_3^-$ and the same genes (Fig. 8).

Despite these distinctions, the environmental variables showed a selective number of gene associations, with some functions (e.g. *amoAa*, *nirK*) being particularly sensitive to NO_3^- content and derived pedological indices rather than to individual parameters. Specifically, the $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NH}_4^+$ ratio proved to be a potentially robust indicator for microbial functional composition, highlighting patterns consistent with the dynamics of availability and competition between nitrogen forms.

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Fig.8 Relationships between pedological variables and soil microbial functions. (a) Correlation between Hellinger dissimilarity of N-C functions and the difference between $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NH}_4^+$, based on the Mantel test. (b) Heatmap of correlations between pedological variables (Corg, NO_3^- , NH_4^+ and their ratios) and log-transformed gene abundances (*nifH*, *amoAb*, *amoAa*, *nirK*, *nirS*, *nosZ*). Statistical significances are indicated with asterisks ($p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ **, $p < 0.001$ ***)

The use of GPS tracking revealed a heterogeneous use of the Malga Juribello pasture (Fig. 9), groupable into 3 macro-areas based on use frequencies (red areas: constant use during the summer period; blue areas: moderate use during the summer period; green areas: sporadic or concentrated use during the summer period – Fig. 9). The most intensively used areas proved to be those in proximity to the malga, where the highest NDVI values were also observed at the end of September (29th September) in both 2023 and 2024 (Fig. 9). This condition coincided with greater late vegetative regrowth. The analysis of late September NDVI maps in relation to the interaction between use classes and vegetation type highlighted a significant increase in values across all vegetation types in areas of constant use (Tab. 7). Conversely, the minimum values were observed in areas of sporadic use. The vegetation types characterised by the highest NDVI values were Poion or Poeto and Rumiceto (Fig. 9). The relationships between NDVI and pasture use estimated on the basis of GPS tracking revealed the potential use of late-summer vegetation spectral indices based on remote sensing applications for assessing the most heavily used areas during the transhumance period. Furthermore, the diversified responses by vegetation type suggest that the use of such indices to assess pasture use should be associated with vegetation maps.

Heatmap Pearson correlation - n.GPS counts

Fig.9 Maps of categorised pasture use (red areas: constant use during the summer period; blue areas: moderate use during the summer period; green areas: sporadic or concentrated use during the summer period) and continuous use (GPS positions), 10m NDVI maps at the end of September 2023 and 2024; Effect of the interaction between vegetation type and use classes on late September NDVI values and their Pearson correlations with normalised counts of GPS positions per pixel.

Tab.7 Results (estimated effects and weighted means) of the spatial GAM models used to analyse the variability of late September NDVI (29th September) and the relationships between vegetation type in interaction with use classes during 2023 and 2024.

	df	F	p-value
tipo_vegetazione:classe_uso	13	136.7	<0.001 ***
	edf	Ref.df	F
			p-value

s(anno)	0.999	1	1	<0.001	***
s(x,y):anno_2023	31.507	31.91	367.3	<0.001	***
s(x,y):anno_2024	30.300	31.11	314.6	<0.001	***
R ²			0.64		
Devianza spiegata			64.1		
RMSE			0.051		

Vegetation	constant use		moderate use		sporadic or concentrated use	
	LSM	95% CI	LSM	95% CI	LSM	95% CI
<i>Nardion</i>	0.63	0.62, 0.63	0.59	0.59, 0.60	0.58	0.57, 0.59
<i>Poion</i>	0.67	0.66, 0.67	0.61	0.61, 0.62	0.61	0.61, 0.62
<i>Poion acido</i>	0.63	0.63, 0.64	0.62	0.61, 0.62	0.59	0.59, 0.60
<i>Poion umido</i>	0.64	0.63, 0.65	0.57	0.57, 0.58	0.57	0.56, 0.58
Romiceto	0.7	0.69, 0.71				
Seslerieto					0.6	0.60, 0.61

At the Monte Coppolo pasture, the analysis of late September NDVI values confirmed the tendency towards late vegetative regrowth in the most heavily grazed areas, especially in the sections used at the beginning of the season (Fig. 10). This suggests a time-mediated vegetation response, a phenomenon that will require future investigations in order to use spectral vegetation indices to assess end-of-season pasture use in different contexts. The analysis of the relationships between pasture use, understood as the normalised count of GPS positions, and NDVI also highlighted differences between the two years, likely linked to weather conditions (Fig. 10).

Fig.10 Relationship between late September NDVI 2023 and 2024 and normalised count of GPS positions per pixel in the different grazed sections at Monte Coppolo. Grey areas represent 95% confidence intervals

The use of camera traps at the Monte Coppolo pasture during the summer of 2024 confirmed the presence of wild ungulates (Roe deer - *Capreolus capreolus* - and Red deer - *Cervus elaphus*) and the arrival of the wolf (*Canis lupus* - Fig. 11). The monitoring of the Lamon sheep flock with camera traps made it possible to document the presence of the wolf in proximity to the enclosures and an attempted predation without any losses, suggesting the effectiveness of the prevention measures implemented (electrified fences and daily shepherd control). The videos recorded by the camera traps will furthermore be used as indirect behavioural observations in association with the accelerometer data from the GPS collars to develop behavioural classification models.

Fig.11 Photos taken by the camera traps used on Monte Coppolo during the summer of 2024 (top left: Lamon sheep with GPS collar; top right: transhumant flock on the pasture in early September; bottom left: male roe deer; bottom right: wolf during nocturnal passage)

The use of the FTIR GASMET GT5000 system made it possible to monitor methane and nitrous oxide emission fluxes at the Malga Juribello pasture. The analysis of fluxes in relation to pasture use intensity (PUI), period (T1: pre-transhumance; T2: during transhumance; T3: post-transhumance) and their interaction revealed a marked variability. The fluxes of both greenhouse gases were not found to be

influenced by use intensity and period, except for methane, which was significantly more emitted during the pre-transhumance period (Fig. 12). The variability observed during monitoring, however, suggests the need to consider additional factors by extending the sample set and its conditions.

Greenhouse gas fluxes were analysed in relation to the microbial functions estimated in the same soil, revealing initial significant associations (Fig. 12). The use of microbial functions as a proxy for actual emissions, however, will require future investigations due to the observed variability.

Fig.12 Methane (CH₄) and Nitrous Oxide (N₂O) emissions at the Malga Juribello pasture in relation to period (T1: pre-transhumance; T2: during transhumance; T3: post-transhumance) and in relation to microbial functions identified in the soil.

During the iMAP project, forages and sheep faeces were sampled at the Monte Coppolo pasture to carry out monitoring of the productive quality of the pasture, to be associated with remote sensing spectral

indices and ovine selective behaviour based on metabarcoding analyses. However, due to delays by the laboratory selected for the chemical analysis of both sample types, it was not possible to integrate the results into the current report.

2. Cost Summary

Cost Items	Details	Supplier	Cost
External personnel costs	Research fellowship renewal	-	8.333,44
Consumable materials	Powersoil Pro 250 Kit (DNA extraction); QUBIT Kit (extracted DNA quantification); 3D batteries for GPS collars	QIAGEN; ThermoFisher; Vectronic Aerospace GmbH	7.247,41
Equipment	Camera traps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 ZEISS Secacam 7 • 5 ICU Cam 6 	Armeria bruschetti	2.849,98
Software	-	-	-
Consultancy – External Services	External sequencing service	NOVOGENE	17.446,00
Publications	Article in Crop and Pasture Science		3.050,00
Indirect costs (15% of personnel costs)			1.250,02
Total Expenses (inclusive of indirect costs)			40.176,85

The iMAP project concluded with overall expenditure in line with the planned budget. Compared to the initial proposal, however, some variations were recorded in the cost items related to consumable materials and consultancy, understood as external services. In particular, in order to comply with the stringent project timelines, it was decided to outsource the analyses to an external laboratory, thus reducing the number of reagents needed for on-site use. This choice, however, led to an increase in costs for external sequencing services, relying on a laboratory already involved in analyses related to iNEST. This allowed experimental continuity with previous trials from a methodological standpoint, while at the same time ensuring adequate timelines and quality standards for the completion of the project. This increase, together with publication costs higher than initially anticipated, resulted in a marginal overrun of the assigned budget, while allowing the full achievement of the project objectives.

Thanks to the iMAP project, it was possible to fund a publication related to one of the two study areas (Malga Juribello pasture – Raniolo et al., 2024, Microbial genes highlight different trends in short term for N cycling in historical alpine pastures, Crop and Pasture Science, 75(10)). The project also made it possible to integrate and expand the molecular and chemical soil

investigation on samples collected prior to the start of activities, providing key preliminary results for developing and improving the adopted operational framework.

Within iMAP, it was also possible to integrate the molecular analyses of additional soil samples previously collected at the Juribello pasture, leading to the publication of a second scientific article (Raniolo et al., 2025, Grazing Intensity Accelerates Surface Soil C and N Cycling in Alpine Pastures as Revealed by Soil Genes and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ Ratio, *Sustainability*, 17(5), 48). The results of both articles were valorised within iNEST through the publication of the dataset "Dataset of microbial genes related to Nitrogen cycle of pasture soil" on the Zenodo iNEST – Spoke 1 platform, thus making them available for future use and further investigation.

3. Future Perspectives

The iMAP project achieved its stated objective of developing an operational framework integrating multiple approaches for monitoring alpine pastures, laying solid foundations for future developments within iNEST in the medium and longer term. The approach adopted in the iMAP project made it possible to further develop the one implemented in the iNEST project, providing multiple outputs that can be directly integrated into the latter ecosystem. Specifically, the results achieved highlighted the complex direct and indirect interactions in the grasslands of the two study areas, confirming the soundness and integration potential of GPS tracking for characterising the animal dimension, remote sensing for characterising the vegetation dimension, and the molecular/chemical approach for the pedological dimension. These integrations made it possible to identify potential pedological indices (e.g. $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{NH}_4^+$) for defining conditions of different pasture use intensity and distinct potential microbial functional profiles, regardless of the monitoring period. Furthermore, the application of NDVI together with GPS tracking allowed the identification of early autumn NDVI values as a possible indicator for assessing seasonal pasture use, laying the groundwork for future research activities aimed at developing non-invasive monitoring tools for farmers and public administrators.

Thanks to the equipment acquired and the data collected, it will be possible to:

- Validate and optimise non-invasive indicators for pasture monitoring;
- Establish geodatabases to be used in future analyses;

- Integrate the results into the iNEST project – RT2: the iMAP data and analyses will contribute to a systemic and integrated approach for the sustainable management of alpine grasslands, especially those dedicated to grazing within mountain extensive livestock systems. The completion of the planned activities and the availability of long-term data represent a significant achievement, which will enable a more effective response to the challenges posed by climate change and natural disturbances in mountain areas.

The project also contributed to the production of the following academic outputs:

Presentations at international conferences:

- Raniolo, S.*, Da Re, S., Sturaro, E., Ramanzin, M. 2025. Pasture-use intensity and Vegetation: Insights from GPS Tracking and Remote Sensing from an alpine pasture. Oral presentation. 76th Annual Meeting of the European Federation of Animal Science, Innsbruck (Austria), 25-29 August 2025;
- Raniolo, S.*, Da Re, S., Squartini, A., Sturaro, E., Ramanzin, M. 2025. Grazing intensity, soil functions and Greenhouse Gas Emissions: a case study in Alpine pastures of the Dolomites. Oral presentation. ASPA 26th Congress, Torino (Italia), 17-20 June 2025;
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